

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

A comprehensive description of the circulating tumor cell: CDH23.

Shahan K. Mamoor, B.S., M.S., Ph.D cand.¹
¹shahanmamoor@gmail.com
Chestnut Hill, MA USA 02467
East Islip, NY USA 11730

The circulating tumor cell (CTC) is most likely responsible for effective metastasis (1-3). We measured total transcription in circulating tumor cells isolated from the blood of women with stage IV breast cancer to define at the molecular level the most significant changes that accompany dissemination in a migrating tumor cell population (4) and integrated these with transcriptomic study of the circulating tumor cell in humans with metastatic prostate cancer (5). We identify here CDH23 as a differentially expressed target in the circulating tumor cell in humans with cancer.

1 Circulating tumor cells are likely the tumor cell population that function in dissemination and do so by
2 seeding distant organ sites. We defined the CTC transcriptome, describing the most significant changes
3 by target and using normal blood cells from the peripheral blood as a control reference transcriptome.

4 Results

5 **Figure 1:** CDH23 is differentially expressed in the circulating tumor cell.

6 I. CTC from humans with stage IV breast cancer (peripheral blood).

7 $n=18$ normal cells from the peripheral blood (human)

8 $n=14$ circulating tumor cells; humans with stage IV breast cancer; peripheral blood

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
64072	4.69E-05	0.535	-4.0705067	-2.1769124	199.18	CDH23	3411/21908	84.4

9
10 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in circulating tumor cells isolated from the
11 peripheral blood of women with stage IV breast cancer and transcription in normal cells of the blood (5),
12 we discovered differential expression of cadherin 23, encoded by *CDH23* in the CTC humans (**Chart 1**).
13 The expression of CDH23 changed more than nearly 85% of the human transcriptome when considering
14 all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 21,908 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the
15 negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CDH23 messenger RNA in the CTC, indicating
16 up-regulation of CDH23 disease progression and metastasis from primary tumor to CTC during the tumor
17 life cycle.

18 II. CTC from humans with stage IV breast cancer (peripheral blood).

19 $n=1$ normal white blood cells from the peripheral blood (human)

20 $n=5$ circulating tumor cells; humans with metastatic prostate cancer ; peripheral blood

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
64072	4.71E-01	2.608	-0.721213	-1.881022	3.75E+02	CDH23	13561/26194	48.2

21 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the CTC of humans with prostate cancer
22 relative to normal white blood cells using a second microarray dataset (6) from independent
23 investigators and a separate patient cohort, we validated differential expression of CDH23 in humans with
24 metastatic solid tumor type. (**Chart 2**). The expression of CDH23 here changed more than half of the
25 human transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case,
26 26,194 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CDH23
27 messenger RNA in the CTC indicating up-regulation of CDH23 disease progression and metastasis from
28 primary tumor to CTC during the tumor life cycle.

Thus, differential and increased expression of CDH23 is a defining change of the circulating tumor cell gene expression signature in humans with metastatic breast cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Discussion

We provided evidence here that CDH23 is a molecular target of modulation in the CTC. This included a panel of cell surface markers, some of whose expression was conserved as marking the CTC in prostate cancer but of some of whose expression was specific to the circulating tumor cell in humans with metastatic breast cancer.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

References

1. Williams, Sarah CP. "Circulating tumor cells." *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 110, no. 13 (2013): 4861-4861.
2. Plaks, V., Koopman, C.D. and Werb, Z., 2013. Circulating tumor cells. *Science*, 341(6151), pp.1186-1188.
3. Cristofanilli, M., Budd, G.T., Ellis, M.J., Stopeck, A., Matera, J., Miller, M.C., Reuben, J.M., Doyle, G.V., Allard, W.J., Terstappen, L.W. and Hayes, D.F., 2004. Circulating tumor cells, disease progression, and survival in metastatic breast cancer. *New England Journal of Medicine*, 351(8), pp.781-791.
4. Ring, A., Campo, D., Porras, T.B., Kaur, P., Forte, V.A., Tripathy, D., Lu, J., Kang, I., Press, M.F., Jeong, Y.J. and Snow, A., 2022. Circulating tumor cell transcriptomics as biopsy surrogates in metastatic breast cancer. *Annals of surgical oncology*, 29(5), pp.2882-2894.
5. Boya, M., Ozkaya-Ahmadov, T., Swain, B.E., Chu, C.H., Asmare, N., Civelekoglu, O., Liu, R., Lee, D., Tobia, S., Biliya, S. and McDonald, L.D., 2022. High throughput, label-free isolation of circulating tumor cell clusters in meshed microwells. *Nature communications*, 13(1), p.3385.

1
2
3
4
5
6
7
8
9
10
11
12
13
14
15
16
17
18
19
20
21
22
23
24
25
26
27
28

Methods

We utilized GSE113890 (4) for this transcriptome study of the circulating tumor cell in humans with cancer, measuring whole transcription in CTC isolated from peripheral blood from humans with stage IV breast cancer, as compared to normal cells from the peripheral blood (along with a second dataset GSE202650 (5) studying the CTC in humans with prostate cancer for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and R-based computational methods (GEO2R).